

**FIRST STEERING
COMMITTEE REPORT**
D-PhD06-6.17

Responsible Partner: ANSES

GENERAL INFORMATION

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<https://www.anses.fr/fr/content/pourquoi-la-tuberculose-bovine-persiste-dans-certaines-r%C3%A9gions-fran%C3%A7aises>